

Development of a Low Bit Error Rate (BER) Coding Technique for Underwater Communication

Dr.Y. Venkata Ratnam^{*1}, Dr.I.Kranthi Kiran^{*2}

^{*1} Lecturer in ECE, Government Polytechnic, Amadalavalasa,532185, Andhra Pradesh, India

^{*2} Professor in the Department of ECE, MVGR College of Engineering(A), Vizianagaram,535005.

ISSN: 3108-1053 (VOLUME-2, ISSUE-1)

Received: January 15, 2026

Revised: January 20, 2026

Accepted: February 10, 2026

Published: March 30, 2026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19472791

Abstract: Underwater communication plays a crucial role in transmitting data below the water's surface. Maintaining the quality of transmitted information is essential, as underwater channels are highly affected by speckle noise and multipath currents, leading to Doppler frequency variations and changing node distances. The reliability of text data over acoustic channels is generally assessed through Bit Error Rate (BER) and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)[2]. Bandwidth efficiency can be improved using appropriate modulation schemes and robust error-control coding techniques. This paper proposes a novel channel coding technique that enhances data security, achieves a lower Bit Error Rate (BER), and operates with a reduced Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) requirement. A comparative performance analysis of the proposed Code is carried out against existing coding schemes such as Convolutional Code, Reed–Solomon (RS) Code, Turbo Code, and Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC) Code for text data transmission in underwater acoustic channels. The evaluation employs different modulation schemes, including M-ary Frequency Shift Keying (M-ary FSK), Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK), and Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM). The results demonstrate that the proposed method improves reliability and efficiency in underwater communication systems.

Keywords: Error reduction coding techniques; Bit Error Rate (BER); Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR); MFSK modulation (M-ary FSK); Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK); and Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM).

1 . Introduction

Underwater communication is widely used for sending and receiving messages below the water's surface[1]. Although there are several ways to achieve this, the most common method involves using acoustic waves. Sea communication is challenging because factors such as multi-path propagation, time reverberations of the channel, limited bandwidth, and strong signal attenuation are more prominent over large distances. Underwater communication uses acoustic waves as the carrier and hence has lower data rates than electromagnetic waves used by terrestrial communication. The frequency of a signal determines the absorption loss, which

increases with increasing distance, ultimately limiting the bandwidth. Therefore, underwater communication uses low-frequency carriers of 8-24 kHz range. Due to the low carrier frequency, the amount of overhead must be minimized. Optimizing power consumption, and achieving bandwidth efficiency present significant challenges[3]. Under these circumstances, low-noise error control codes combined with suitable modulation techniques are necessary.

2. Study Area

The two most popular error control coding techniques are the Automatic Repeat Request (ARQ) technique and the Forward Error Correction (FEC) code technique. ARQ is effective for ensuring an adequate packet delivery ratio by utilizing "stop and wait" protocols, but it introduces high latency due to retransmissions. Additionally, some systems do not support full-duplex transmission, which prevents retransmissions. Therefore, FEC codes such as convolution code, Reed-Solomon code, turbo code, polar code, and Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC) code are employed. These powerful codes provide a low Bit Error Rate (BER) but reduce throughput due to the addition of extra bits. To improve the reliability of transmission in challenging and noisy underwater channels, Algorithm-based codes are proposed by applying a supervisory learning algorithm to existing FEC codes, such as convolution code, Reed-Solomon code, LDPC code, turbo code, and polar code[4]. This approach aims to provide a low BER while enhancing transmission reliability. The transmitter sends the signal into the communication channel through the digital modulator. Digital modulation provides several advantages, including increased information capacity, data security, effective use of the RF spectrum, and improved communication quality.

Various digital modulation schemes, such as Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM), Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK), and M-ary Frequency Shift Keying (MFSK), are employed to achieve better spectral efficiency.

This paper focuses on performance evaluation of convolution code, RS code, turbo code, LDPC code with their proposed corresponding Upgraded codes for transmission of an data and image by comparing performance parameters of BER, visual quality, through underwater channel by using M-ary FSK modulation, Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM), Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK).

3. Methodology

Underwater communication is carried out through a modelled underwater channel. The FEC coding and decoding Schemes used were Convolution / Up convolution / RS / LDPC / UP LDPC / Polar / UP Polar, modulation schemes were M-ary FSK, QPSK, or QAM, and channel estimation techniques used were LS/MMSE/Modified- LS Channel.

3.1 Enhancement of existing Error correction codes by using a supervised learning Algorithm:

3.1.1 Upgraded convolution/RS/LDPC/polar code: The message to be transmitted is first encrypted and converted into source code. Each encrypted coded data is encoded by a Convolution/RS/LDPC/POLAR code[16] with a message length of k and a code length of n [6]. This encrypted convolution code is then encoded into an octal code ranging from 0 to 7. Each octal digit is again encoded into a predetermined number of integer patterns varying from 0 to 63. Unique frequency is to be transmitted through the channel for each integer. In this way, Network security can be established with this new coding technique, named as Upgraded convolution code with a code rate of 0.26. Upgraded RS code with a code rate of 0.28. Upgraded LDPC code with a code rate of 0.26. Upgraded Polar code with a code rate of 0.31 with[16]low BER.

3.1.2 Upgraded convolution/RS/LDPC/polar decoder: The upgraded decoder uses narrow-band filters to tune to these frequencies corresponding to integers. It uses supervised learning of decision tree classification. From the labelled dataset, the training dataset is modelled. The type of training dataset is determined first as follows.

A Collection of the training data. The training dataset can be divided into a training labelled dataset, a test labelled dataset, and a validation labelled dataset. Set the features of the labelled training dataset, which have enough knowledge over the dataset, so that the model can accurately predict the output. Apply a decision tree learning algorithm to the model. The decision tree learning algorithm is executed on the training dataset and validates the sets as the control parameter sets, and becomes a subset of the training dataset. After completion of the training process, the model is tested based on a test data set, and then the algorithm chooses the output as a predetermined number of integer patterns. An octal digit is decoded for each integer pattern and then applied to the corresponding decoders to obtain the source code. This source code is now decrypted to get a message

3.2 Digital Modulation Types

Three fundamental types of Digital modulation techniques are commonly used. They are Phase Shift Keying, Frequency Shift Keying, and Amplitude Shift Keying, abbreviated as PSK, FSK, and ASK, respectively. Engineers combine modulation techniques[15] to create more advanced schemes, of Quadrature Amplitude Modulation, Quadrature Phase Shift Keying, Differential Phase Shift Keying, abbreviated as QAM, QPSK, DPSK, respectively, and M-ary Frequency Modulation schemes.

3.3 Underwater acoustic modelled channel and channel estimation techniques

3.3.1: Underwater acoustic modelled channel has wave reverberations, limited bandwidth, and strong attenuation of the signal, which are more prominent over large distances. In order to lessen the shift in Doppler frequency, the ambiguity in the Doppler frequency shift estimation should be less than the frequency variation[14]. The loss of acoustic signal transmission in underwater channels is a combination of absorption loss, spreading loss, and loss due to different paths of propagation of the acoustic signal. This uses three paths with path delays $[0 \ 1.0e-3 \ 100e-3]$ with path gains $[0 \ -1 \ -9]$. The channel estimation techniques used were LSE, MMSE, Modified -LSE..

3.3.2: LEAST SQUARE ERROR (LSE): LSE[8]z is a standard method in a regression system to approximate the result for over-determined systems. Consider every single equation and process the received signal by minimising the sum of the squares of the errors that occur.

3.3.3: MINIMUM MEAN SQUARE ERROR: MMSE is also a standard estimation method in which the mean square error can be minimised, which is a common measure of estimator quality for a dependent variable.

3.3.4: Modified LEAST SQUARE ERROR (Modified-LSE): This approach follows the LS Algorithm; the modification [13]is that the next estimation of the channel can be obtained by averaging the present and previous channel estimations, the averaging value is now treated as the previous channel estimator, and this process is repeated for a predetermined number of iterations.

3. 4 System design model

Figure 1: The block diagram of an underwater modelled communication system

Figure 1 presents a block diagram of underwater communication. The message is being entered through a keyboard. The source encoder transfers the message into a binary data stream. This stream is encoded by the FEC encoder into an encoded stream of bits or symbols. The encoded data is then modulated using M-ary FSK, QPSK, or QAM. The modulated data is transmitted through an underwater channel [5] modelled with two multi-path delays and Doppler shifts ranging from 1 Hz to 201 Hz, in a noisy environment with a specified SNR. Upon reception, the noisy modulated data is demodulated and decoded by the corresponding decoders. Finally, the source decoder translates the binary data stream back into the original message.

4. Results and analysis

4.1 BER Performance of MFSK modulation in an Underwater modelled channel

Figure 2 and Table 1 show the Doppler frequency shift in Hz vs. Bit Error Rate for

existing codes and the proposed codes of Upgraded convolution, Upgraded LDPC, and Upgraded Polar, with SNR of 1 dB in MFSK modulation.

Figure 2: BER performance of existing codes and proposed codes with MFSK modulation

Doppler frequency shift in Hz	Convolution	Upgraded Convolution	TURBO	RS	Upgraded RS	LDPC	Upgraded LDPC	Polar	Upgraded Polar
1	0.474	0.486	0.521	0.322	0.286	0.322	0.281	0.499	0.486
21	0.469	0.499	0.489	0.204	0.201	0.195	0.176	0.504	0.441
41	0.479	0.524	0.504	0.183	0.168	0.195	0.168	0.521	0.341
61	0.045	0.000	0.085	0.000	0.000	0.005	0.010	0.125	0.000

81	0.000	0.000	0.030	0.000	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.085	0.000
101	0.015	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.000	0.000
121	0.045	0.000	0.085	0.021	0.010	0.005	0.007	0.038	0.000
141	0.148	0.030	0.198	0.012	0.021	0.018	0.022	0.296	0.000
161	0.110	0.000	0.068	0.000	0.000	0.010	0.002	0.216	0.000
181	0.035	0.000	0.028	0.012	0.015	0.010	0.016	0.100	0.000
201	0.411	0.030	0.331	0.144	0.100	0.083	0.050	0.431	0.020

Table 1: BER performance of existing codes and proposed codes with MFSK

From Figure 2 and Table 1, It is noted from figure 1 and table 2 that the upgraded polar code (proposed code) BER performance is better by providing low BER ranges from **zero to 0.020** than LDPC BER ranges from **zero to 0.1**, upgraded LDPC BER ranges from **zero to 0.050**, polar BER ranges from **0.038 to 0.431**, upgraded RS code BER ranges from **zero to 0.144**, RS code BER ranges from **zero to 0.331**, upgraded convolution code BER ranges from **zero to 0.030** convolution code BER ranges from **0.015 to 0.411** across Doppler frequency variations above 41 Hz to 201 Hz in MFSK modulation. Doppler frequency variations below 41 Hz in MFSK modulation the upgraded LDPC code (proposed code) BER performance is better with low BER ranges from **0.176 to 0.281** than LDPC BER ranges from **0.2 to 0.32**, upgraded polar BER ranges from **0.341 to 0.48**, polar BER ranges from **0.499 to 0.521**, upgraded RS code BER ranges from **0.168 to 0.286**, RS code BER ranges from **0.183 to 0.322**, upgraded convolution code BER ranges from **0.486 to 0.524**, convolution code BER ranges from **0.469 to 0.479**, at SNR of 1 dB and

with two multi-path delays of 1 m second and 100 m seconds.

Figure 3 (a): BER performance of existing codes with corresponding upgraded codes

Figure 3(b): BER performance of LDPC code with Upgraded LDPC code

Figure 3(c): BER performance of Polar code with Upgraded polar code

Figure 3(d): BER performance of Convolution code with Upgraded Convolution code

It is observed from Figure 3(a),3(b),3(c) and 3(d) that upgraded codes' BER performance is better by providing low BER at an SNR of 1 dB with two multi-path delays of 1 m second and 100 m seconds across most of the Doppler frequency variations 1 Hz to 201 Hz in MFSK modulation.

4.2 BER Performance of various modulation techniques of MFSK/QPSK/QAM in an Underwater modelled channel using upgraded POLAR

Figure 4: BER performance of Upgraded polar in MFSK/QPSK/QAM Modulation

From Figure 4, it is observed that the upgraded polar code (proposed code) with MFSK modulation with SNR of 1 dB provides low BER ranges from zero to 0.45 over QAM provides BER ranges from 0.48 to 0.52 with SNR of 15 dB and QPSK modulation scheme provides BER ranges from zero to 0.48 with two multi-path delays of 1 m second and 100 m seconds, Doppler frequency shifts of 1 Hz to 201 Hz at SNR of 15 dB. Upgraded polar code (proposed code) with MFSK modulation provides zero BER from Doppler frequency shifts 61 Hz to 201 Hz, except at 141 Hz frequency shift (also provides low BER of 0.01). The upgraded polar code (proposed code) with QPSK provides 0.4 BER at selected frequencies of 21 Hz, 101 Hz, and 181 Hz, which is less than the upgraded polar code (proposed code) with QAM (BER more than 0.5).

4.3 JPEG and Sonar image Visual quality using MFSK modulation in an

underwater channel for various codes

Figures 5. (i) and 5. (ii) present the Visual quality of JPEG using MFSK modulation in an underwater modelled channel for various codes

Figure 5(i): Visual quality of JPEG image of Upgraded POLAR and POLAR codes with MFSK

Figure 5(ii): Visual quality of Sonar image of Upgraded POLAR and POLAR codes

From figures 5(i) and 5(ii), it is concluded that the images transmitted by Upgraded polar codes deliver better visibility than their standard counterparts at an SNR of 1 dB and with two multi-path delays of 1 m seconds and 100 m seconds across most Doppler frequency variations of 1 Hz in MFSK modulation.

4.4. BER Performance of MFSK modulation with channel estimation techniques in an Underwater modelled channel

Figure 6: BER performance of OFDM-MFSK modulation with upgraded polar code, along with channel estimation techniques

From Figure 6, it is observed that upgraded polar code with MFSK-COFDM along with Modified LS channel estimation performs better by providing comparatively low BER ranges from zero to 0.02 Bit Error Rate, whereas upgraded polar code with no channel estimation technique BER ranges from 0.1 to 0.46, LS channel estimation provides BER ranges from 0.15 to 0.46 and MMSE channel estimation provides BER 0.47 to 0.5 for Doppler frequency variations of 1 Hz to 201 Hz at SNR of 15 dB, two multi-path delays of 1 m second and 100m seconds. It is also observed that upgraded polar code provides zero Bit Error Rate for all Doppler frequency variations of 1 Hz to 181 Hz Doppler frequency variation and after 181 Hz also it provides low BER of less than 0.1 whereas upgraded polar code with no channel estimation techniques, LS and MMSE provides BER greater than 0.1 for all Doppler frequency variations of with 1 Hz to 201 Hz at SNR of 15 dB, two multi-path delays of 1 m second and 100m seconds.

Conclusion

The simulation results demonstrate that the upgraded polar code consistently outperforms other coding techniques across varying Doppler frequencies and modulation schemes. In high Doppler conditions, it achieves significantly lower BER, often approaching zero, compared to LDPC, RS, and convolution codes. Under low Doppler conditions, upgraded LDPC shows competitive performance, but the proposed polar code remains robust overall. With MFSK modulation and Modified LS channel estimation, the upgraded polar code delivers superior reliability, maintaining minimal BER even under multipath delays and varying SNR levels. Hence, it is an effective solution for enhancing communication performance in dynamic wireless environments.

Acknowledgements

We thank Dr CH Raju and Bharani, Government Polytechnic, Visakhapatnam, for their support.

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